

“PALACE OF THE KHOREZMSHAKH”

Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnubek ugli

Independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10704291>

The Tashhavli Palace in Khiva, which is still luring the famous, still worldly people, was built in 1829-1839 by order of Ollakulikhan (1794-1842) on the project of Minister Mukhammad Ya'kub Mekhtar. This palace was built as the second Arch in Khiva, the palace of the ruler-Khan. The name of the stone courtyard, built of baked bricks, comes from the distinctive plan and architecture of the building. In ancient times, the buildings were short-lived because they were built of raw clay and carcass (*wood*). Later, brick was baked in humbuses, and stone structures began to be built. Therefore, to distinguish them from each other, names appeared, and the word “Stone” was applied to many castles. For example, there are no few buildings and structures in stone Kent, stone pond, Khiva, which are called by the name of Stone: Stone mosque, stone bridge, Stone Gate, Stone Well (*well*), Stone Street, stone lamp, sickle stone, etc. The stone courtyard Palace consists of three large (a lookout, a hotel, a harem) and five small courtyards, a two-story porch, and rooms. First the Haram, then the hotel, and later the complaints courtyards were completed. While Khan's family lived in the harem, the hotel served such great guests as the ambassador from abroad, the Turkmen captain and the Karakalpak Biri. When the attention of the citizen was heard in complain, ambassadors from abroad were officially received here.

On the orders of Ollakulikhan, the Toshhovuz fortress was rebuilt in 1835 by Mukhammad Yusuf Mekhtar, the Sultan Uways Kariani and Sheikh Mukhammad Okhund Kharezmiy mausoleums in Kat fortress in 1836-1838, as well as the Sulaiman Boğirghani-Khakim OTA mausoleums in Kurgkhat. Olloculichon called one healer from the Prince and three judges from India through King Kamron of Herot in 1830, sponsoring the development of medicine science in the country.

This ruler passed away in 258 (1842) on the night of Tuesday, the 3rd day of the month of zulqa'da. He lived for 49 years and was Khan for 18 years. He left a name in history as just, shariathist, Valiant and brave Khan. His sessions included a discussion of history and ghazal, anecdotal. He was survived by seven sons, two of whom-Rakhimkuli Tora and Mukhammad Amin inok-reigned in the Khanate's office.

The Toshkhavli Palace features the most beautiful works of a Kharezmian architect, a master of carving Nakkash, koshinpaz, wood and marble. It is possible to create an image until you can see how beautiful the palace is. This was stated by many poetic histories of the phosils of his time at the time of the construction of the palace. Some of them are finished in tin decorations inside the palace.

The Armory, known as the Toshhovli lookout or reception hall, is also a high porch courtyard like the one in the Kohna Ark (Old castle), in front of which also a tall rounded porch was built. A hearth was placed on top of this soup, where guests were given a feast.

This is how Abdullakh Boltaev (1890-1966), who saw and heard the reception of Khan in complaints office firsthand, recorded it. "At the reception, the Khan will be surrounded by yasuwulboshi, Mekhtar, Kushbegi, shotirs (the retainer of Khan's horse, they are four on two sides of Khan's horse wearing red clothes and hanging bells around their waist) and other servants. The porch is lined with carpets, Palos, fine felt, on which tiger skin is thrown. Khan leaves the harem every day, two and a half hours before sunset, sits on the throne next to the pillar of the complaints office porch and proceeds to listen to complaints. One of the shots goes up to the gate and alternately calls the cheaters to the reception. The one who comes to arz begins with the word "there was a fault, a trifle". Khan begins to tell him what he is worth after he looks at him and says "Tell me what you are worth". Those who come to arz enter through one door and leave through the other".

After the reception at the complaints office, Khan enters his room and sits down. After that, all the close officials enter the "salute" to Khan and give him a look. Only after the Khan enters his harem, that is, inside, they go home.

It is also possible to know that the hotel was built for the honored guests of the Khan-that even

ambassadors from abroad were sent down to the House of some rich man or official. He was invited to the palace only after Khan told him when he would accept. The presence of their friends in the capital of such respected guests as Turkmen captains in the Khanate or Kazakh and Karakalpak Biri would not have created the need for a hotel for them. Khan would invite them to the hotel if he wanted to. The construction definition of this courtyard can be found in the inscriptions on the tiles of the wall of the hotel porch.

On the net of the hotel porch, on the wooden door of the room, which is entered from the south wall, is written the following prayer, Arabic, Nasta'lik letter:

Let this magnificent castle always keep the state and victories.

The hotel consists of a courtyard surrounded by two-story rooms, and the net of a high porch on the south side of the courtyard houses the most beautiful rooms on the first and second floors. The room on the first floor is covered with beautifully patterned blue tiles from the bottom to the top, the ceiling is decorated with stucco patterns in gold and red. The room on the second floor is finally enriched with examples of hand carving, wood and copper carving work, which are elaborately elaborated. In the middle of the courtyard are placed two chimneys designed for the installation of a fireplace.

References:

1. Ismailov, T. (2022, November). THE FORT THAT SPEAKS FROM THE PAST. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 18-22).
2. Ismailov, T. (2024). KO'HNA VA HAMISHA NAVQIRON SHAHAR. Молодые ученые, 2(2), 71-72.

